

CCAENA QUESTIONNAIRE – CONTINUITY OF CARE BETWEEN CARE LEVELS

A. INTERVIEW INFORMATION

1. Locality:	___ ___
2. Interviewer:	___ ___ ___
3. Date of interview:	___ ___ / ___ ___ / ___ ___
Start time:	4. Duration (minutes) ___ ___
End time:	
5. Patient's Primary care centre:	___ ___
6. Interview location	
1 Home 2 Primary care centre 3 Café, bar 4 Outdoors 5 Workplace	
6 Other: Specify.....	

INFORMATION FOR THE INTERVIEWEE

We are currently doing a study to identify the strengths and weaknesses of our health care services. A survey is being performed as part of this research to find out what patients think of the different health services they use.

The information which you will provide is very important, as it helps us to identify problems with the services and to make changes with view to improving the care offered in the primary care centres and in hospitals.

The people who make use of this information are obliged to comply with the law on statistical confidentiality, meaning that they cannot divulge it to other parties or use it for any purpose other than that described above, so we can ensure that the data will remain confidential.

(Articles 37, 38 and 39 of Law 23/1998 , 30th December)

Thank you for participating in this study.

B. MEDICAL HISTORY

*** Now I'm going to ask you a question about your health**

7. In the last three months, for what health problems or illnesses have you consulted your GP and also the specialist or hospital? _____

*** Now I'm going to ask you some questions about ____ CITE REASON FOR CONSULTATION (QUESTION 7)**

8. How long have you had _____? CITE REASON FOR CONSULTATION (QUESTION 7)

____ months or ____ years _____

9. Which was the first place you consulted regarding _____?

- | | | | |
|---|------------------------------------|-----------------------------|-----------------------------|
| 1 Primary care centre | 2 Specialist visit (as outpatient) | 3 Hospital A&E | 4 When admitted to hospital |
| 5 Emergency department at primary care centre | | 6 Private healthcare centre | 7 Medical check-up |
| 98 Does not reply | 99 Does not know | 8 Other. Specify: | |

10. Where were you informed that you had _____?

- | | | | |
|---|------------------------------------|-----------------------------|-----------------------------|
| 1 Primary care centre | 2 Specialist visit (as outpatient) | 3 Hospital A&E | 4 When admitted to hospital |
| 5 Emergency department at primary care centre | | 6 Private healthcare centre | 7 Medical check-up |
| 8 Undiagnosed | 98 Does not reply | 99 Does not know | 9 Other. Specify |

11. Who is/are the person(s) responsible for treating your _____?

- | | | | |
|------------------|-----------------------|--------|-------------------|
| 1 GP | 2 Specialist | 3 Both | 98 Does not reply |
| 99 Does not know | Other. Specify: | | |

12. How long have you been seeing the doctor(s) responsible for treating your _____?

GP: _____ months or _____ years Specialist: _____ months or _____ years _____

13. Due to your _____, in the last year, have you always visited the same GP? VISITS TO A&E AT THE PRIMARY CARE CENTRE ARE NOT INCLUDED

- 1 Yes → go to question 16 2 No 8 Does not reply → go to question 16 99 Does not know → go to question 16

ONLY FOR PATIENTS WHO HAVE VISITED MORE THAN ONE GP

14. As a result of your _____, how many doctors from the primary health centre have you seen in the last year? _____

15. Why did you see another GP?

- | | | |
|----------------------------------|-------------------------|---|
| 1 My doctor was off work | 2 My doctor was changed | 3 My doctor was away on holiday |
| 4 I requested a change of doctor | 98 Does not reply | 99 Does not know 5 Other. Specify: |

FOR ALL PATIENTS INTERVIEWED

16. As a result of your _____, in the last year, have you always been treated by the same specialist doctor (as an outpatient)? READ ALL POSSIBLE ANSWERS. DOCTORS WHO TREATED THE PATIENT IN A&E OR WHEN ADMITTED TO HOSPITAL ARE NOT INCLUDED. REFERS TO ONE SOLE MEDICAL SPECIALITY: THE ONE WHICH THEY HAVE VISITED MOST OFTEN.

- 1 Yes → go to question 19 2 No 3 I have not visited any specialists as an outpatient → go to question 19
98 Does not reply → go to question 19 99 Does not know → go to question 19

ONLY FOR PATIENTS WHO HAVE VISITED MORE THAN ONE SPECIALIST

17. As a result of your _____, how many specialist doctors have treated you as an outpatient in the last year? _____

18. Why did you see another doctor?

- | | | |
|----------------------------------|-------------------------|---|
| 1 My doctor was off work | 2 My doctor was changed | 3 My doctor was away on holiday |
| 4 I requested a change of doctor | 98 Does not reply | 99 Does not know 5 Other. Specify: |

C. USE OF HEALTHCARE SERVICES

*** Now I'm going to ask you a series of questions on the care you've received in the last 3 months for _____ CITE REASON FOR CONSULTATION (QUESTION 7)**

Care level	Location of consultation	19. Where have you consulted doctors regarding ___ in the last three months?	20. How many times have you been seen there?
Primary care	Primary care centre		
Secondary care	Specialist outpatient		
	Hospital A&E		
	Hospital inpatient		

21. In what order did you consult them? INDICATE THE ORDER IN WHICH ALL THE SERVICES WERE USED IN THE LAST THREE MONTHS FOR THE SAME CONDITION. A SERVICE CAN BE SELECTED MORE THAN ONCE, BUT ONLY ONE BOX MAY BE SELECTED IN EACH COLUMN.

Care level	Location of consultation	Order of consultation							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Primary care	Primary care centre								
Secondary care	Specialist outpatient								
	Hospital A&E								
	Hospital inpatient								

Diagram of visits

THIS TABLE IS SHOWN AS A GUIDE FOR THE INTERVIEWER

Care level	Location of consultation	Order of consultation									
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Primary care	Primary care centre	X		X	X			X			X
Secondary care	Specialist outpatient		X								
	Hospital A&E				X				X		
	Hospital inpatient					X		X			
Is there a change in level? (Y/N)		-	Y	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	Y
Section to be filled in		-	4	1	-	5	-	3	6	-	2

Go through the sections for which the patient has undergone a change in care level

If they visited a GP after visiting the specialist	→ go through section 1
If they visited a GP after visiting hospital A&E	→ go through section 2
If they visited a GP after being discharged from hospital	→ go through section 3
If they visited specialist health care after visiting their GP	→ go through section 4
If they visited hospital A&E after visiting their GP	→ go through section 5
If they were admitted to hospital after visiting their GP	→ go through section 6

1. GP after visiting the SPECIALIST

Order of consultation _____

*** The questions I'm going to ask you now refer to the care you received from your GP after consulting the specialist**

22. Did the specialist send you to your GP?

- 1 Yes → go to question 24 2 No 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

23. Why did you visit your GP?

- 1 To get prescriptions 2 My GP had told me to come back again
 3 To inform him/her of the visit with the specialist 4 To get signed off work/ declared fit for work
 5 I felt unwell 6 Other. Specify:

24. Where was your appointment to see the GP arranged?

- 1 Primary care centre 2 Hospital 3 Health information hotline 4 Other. Specify:

25. How many days passed between visiting the specialist and seeing your GP?

Days _____

26. How many days did it take from requesting an appointment until you saw your GP?

Days _____

27. What is your view on that amount of waiting time?

- 1 Adequate 2 Long 3 Excessive 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

28. Did the specialist give you a medical report to be handed in to your GP?

- 1 Yes 2 No 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

29. Was your GP aware of the instructions given to you by the specialist? (medication, check-ups, etc.) READ OUT POSSIBLE ANSWERS

- 1 Yes 2 No 3 I wasn't given any instructions 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

30. Was your GP aware of the treatment prescribed by the specialist? READ OUT POSSIBLE ANSWERS

- 1 Yes 2 No 3 I wasn't prescribed any treatments → go to question 35 98 Does not reply
 99 Does not know

31. Did your GP give you any explanations about the treatment prescribed by the specialist?

- 1 Yes 2 No 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

32. Was your GP in agreement with the treatment prescribed by the specialist?

- 1 Yes 2 No 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

33. Did your GP make any changes to the treatment prescribed by the specialist?

- 1 Yes 2 No → go to question 35 98 Does not reply → go to question 35 99 Does not know → go to question 35

34. What changes did he/she make?

- 1 Withdrew the treatment 2 Changed the instructions for the treatment 3 Changed the dosage of the treatment
 4 Added another treatment 5 Changed it for a similar one 6 Other. Specify:

35. Did your GP resolve any doubts regarding your visit to the specialist? READ OUT POSSIBLE ANSWERS

- 1 Yes 2 No 3 I had no doubts 4 I didn't ask 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

36A. Do you think your care was well coordinated in the transition from the specialist to your GP?

- 1 Yes 2 No 3 Partially 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

36B. Why?

2. GP after visiting hospital A&E

Order of consultation _____

* The questions I'm going to ask you now refer to the care you received from your GP after having visited A&E at the hospital

37. Did the doctor at A&E send you for a check-up with your GP?

- 1 Yes → go to question 39 2 No 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

38. Why did you visit your GP?

- 1 To get prescriptions 2 My GP told me to come back again
 3 To inform him/her of the visit with the A&E doctor 4 To get signed off work/ declared fit for work
 5 I felt unwell 6 Other. Specify:

39. Where was your appointment to see the GP arranged?

- 1 Primary care centre 2 Hospital 3 Health information hotline 4 Other. Specify:

40. How many days passed between visiting the hospital A&E and seeing your GP?

Days _____

41. How many days did it take from requesting an appointment until you saw your GP?

Days _____

42. What is your view on that amount of waiting time from requesting an appointment until being seen?

- 1 Adequate 2 Long 3 Excessive 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

43. Did the A&E doctor give you a report for your GP?

- 1 Yes 2 No 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

44. Was your GP aware of the instructions given to you in A&E? (medication, check-ups, etc.) *READ OUT POSSIBLE ANSWERS*

- 1 Yes 2 No 3 I wasn't given any instructions 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

45. Was your GP aware of the treatment prescribed by the A&E doctor?*READ OUT POSSIBLE ANSWERS*

- 1 Yes 2 No 3 I wasn't prescribed any treatments → go to question 35
 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

46. Did your GP give you any explanations about the treatment prescribed by the A&E doctor?

- 1 Yes 2 No 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

47. Was your GP in agreement with the treatment prescribed by the A&E doctor?

- 1 Yes 2 No 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

48. Did your GP make any changes to the treatment prescribed by the A&E doctor?

- 1 Yes 2 No → go to question 50 98 Does not reply → go to question 50 99 Does not know → go to question 50

49. What changes did he/she make?

- 1 Withdrew the treatment 2 Changed the instructions for the treatment 3 Changed the dosage of the treatment
 4 Added another treatment 5 Changed it for a similar one 6 Other. Specify:

50. Did your GP resolve any doubts regarding your visit to the A&E doctor? *READ OUT POSSIBLE ANSWERS*

- 1 Yes 2 No 3 I had no doubts 4 I didn't ask 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

51A. Do you think your care was well coordinated in the transition from the A&E doctor to your GP?

- 1 Yes 2 No 3 Partially 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

51B. Why?

3. GP after being DISCHARGED FROM HOSPITAL

Order of consultation _____

* The questions I'm going to ask you now refer to the care you received from your GP after having been discharged from hospital

52. When you were discharged from hospital, were you told that you had to visit your GP?

- 1 Yes → go to question 54 2 No 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

53. Why did you visit your GP?

- 1 To get prescriptions 2 My GP told me to come back again
 3 To inform him/her of the visit with the specialist 4 To get signed off work/ declared fit for work 5 I felt unwell
 6 Other. Specify:

54. Where was your appointment to see the GP arranged?

- 1 Primary care centre 2 Hospital 3 Health information hotline 4 Other. Specify:

55. How many days passed between being discharged from hospital and seeing your GP?

Days ____

56. How many days did it take from requesting an appointment until you saw your GP?

Days ____

57. What is your view on that amount of waiting time from requesting an appointment until being seen?

- 1 Adequate 2 Long 3 Excessive 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

58. Did the doctor at the hospital give you report about your hospitalization?

- 1 Yes 2 No 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

59. Was your GP aware of the instructions given to you at the hospital? (medication, check-ups, etc.)*READ OUT POSSIBLE ANSWERS*

- 1 Yes 2 No 3 I wasn't given any instructions 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

60. Was your GP aware of the treatment prescribed at the hospital? *READ OUT POSSIBLE ANSWERS*

- 1 Yes 2 No 3 I wasn't prescribed any treatments → go to question 65 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

61. Did your GP give you any explanations about the treatment prescribed at the hospital?

- 1 Yes 2 No 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

62. Was your GP in agreement with the treatment prescribed at the hospital?

- 1 Yes 2 No 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

63. Did your GP make any changes to the treatment prescribed at the hospital?

- 1 Yes 2 No → go to question 65 98 Does not reply → go to question 65 99 Does not know → go to question 65

64. What changes did he/she make?

- 1 Withdrew the treatment 2 Changed the instructions for the treatment 3 Changed the dosage of the treatment
 4 Added another treatment 5 Changed it for a similar one 6 Other. Specify:

65. Did your GP resolve any doubts regarding your hospitalization? *READ OUT POSSIBLE ANSWERS*

- 1 Yes 2 No 3 I had no doubts 4 I didn't ask 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

66A. Do you think your care was well coordinated in the transition from the hospital to your GP?

- 1 Yes 2 No 3 Partially 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

66B. Why?

4. SPECIALIST CARE after seeing the GP

Order of consultation ____

* The questions I'm going to ask you now refer to the care you received from the specialist after having seen your GP

67. Did your GP send you to visit the specialist?

- 1 Yes → go to question 69 2 No 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

68. Why did you visit the specialist?

- 1 Appointment was arranged by the specialist 2 I was sent there from the hospital 3 Other. Specify:

69. Where was your appointment to see the specialist arranged?

- 1 Primary care centre 2 Hospital 3 Other. Specify:

70. How many days did it take from requesting an appointment until you saw the specialist?

Days: _____ or Weeks: _____ or Months: _____

71. What is your view on the amount of waiting time from requesting an appointment until being seen?

1 Adequate 2 Long 3 Excessive 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

72. Was the specialist who saw you aware of the reason why your GP sent you? READ OUT POSSIBLE ANSWERS

1 Yes 2 No 3 I wasn't sent by my GP 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

73. Did the specialist already have information about your other illnesses? READ OUT POSSIBLE ANSWERS

1 Yes 2 No 3 I don't have any other illnesses 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

74. Was the specialist aware of the results of the tests which were performed on you in primary care? READ OUT POSSIBLE ANSWERS

1 Yes 2 No 3 I didn't have any tests done 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

75. Was the specialist already aware of any medicines you were taking? READ OUT POSSIBLE ANSWERS

1 Yes 2 No 3 I wasn't taking any medicines 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

76A. Do you think your care was well coordinated in the transition from the specialist to your GP?

1 Yes 2 No 3 Partially 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

76B. Why?_____

_____**5. HOSPITAL A&E after visiting the GP****Order of consultation** _____*** The questions I'm going to ask you now refer to the care you received from A&E at the hospital****77. Who made the decision to go to the hospital A&E?**1 I made it myself 2 A doctor at the Primary care centre → go to question 79A
3 A family member or companion 4 Emergency medical services → go to question 79A 5 Other. Specify:.....**78. Why didn't you go to the primary care centre first?**1 It was closed 2 The care is better in A&E 3 I don't like going to the clinic
4 I was told to go to A&E if my condition got worse 5 Other. Specify:.....**79A. Do you think that the doctors who saw you in A&E were aware of your medical history?**

1 Yes 2 No 98 Does not reply → go to question 80 99 Does not know → go to question 80

79B. Why?_____

_____**80. Did you have to explain the instructions which your GP gave you to the A&E doctor? (medication, check-ups,...) READ OUT POSSIBLE ANSWERS**

1 Yes 2 No 3 I wasn't given any instructions 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

6. ADMISSION TO HOSPITAL after seeing the GP**Order of consultation** _____*** The questions I'm going to ask you now refer to the care you received from your during your hospitalization****81A. Do you think that the doctors who saw you in the hospital were aware of your medical history?**

1 Yes 2 No 98 Does not reply → go to question 82 99 Does not know → go to question 82

81B. Why?_____

_____**82. Did you have to explain the instructions which your GP gave you to the hospital doctor? (medication, check-ups,...) READ OUT POSSIBLE ANSWERS**

1 Yes 2 No 3 I wasn't given any instructions 98 Does not reply 99 Does not know

D. PERCEPTION OF CONTINUITY OF CARE

FOR ALL PATIENTS INTERVIEWED

* The questions I'm going to ask you now are about your general opinion of the care you have received for all the illnesses for which you have been treated

INFORMATIONAL CONTINUITY: Transfer of medical information

* Rate the following statements according to these categories: always, often, rarely and never

	Always	Often	Rarely	Never	Not applicable	Does not reply	Does not know
83. I believe that the professionals attending to me know my previous medical history							
84. After seeing the specialist, my GP discusses the visit with me							
85. My GP is aware of the instructions given to me by the specialist before I explain them to him/her							
86. The specialist is aware of the instructions given to me by my GP before I explain them to him/her							

MANAGERIAL CONTINUITY: Care coherence

* Rate the following statements according to these categories: always, often, rarely and never

	Always	Often	Rarely	Never	Not applicable	Does not reply	Does not know
87. My GP is in agreement with the specialist's instructions							
88. My GP and my specialist communicate with each other							
89. The specialist is usually in agreement with my GP's instructions							
90A. The specialist repeats the tests which my GP has already done (blood tests, x-rays, etc.)							
90B. Why?							___ ___ ___
91. The specialist makes out the first prescription for the treatment he/she prescribes me							
92. The specialist sends me to my GP for follow-ups							
93A. I believe that the care I receive from my GP and the specialist is coordinated							
93B. Why?							___ ___ ___

MANAGERIAL CONTINUITY: Accessibility between levels

* Rate the following statements according to these categories: always, often, rarely and never

	Always	Often	Rarely	Never	Not applicable	Does not reply	Does not know
94. My appointments with the specialist are arranged at the primary care centre							
95. When I request an appointment with my GP, I have to wait a long time to see him/her							
96. The centre where I am seen by the specialist schedules my follow-up visits with my GP							
97. When I request an appointment with the specialist, I have to wait a long time to see him/her							

RELATIONAL CONTINUITY: patient-provider relationship

* Rate the following statements according to these categories: totally agree, agree, disagree and totally disagree

GP	Totally agree	Agree	Disagree	Totally disagree	Not applicable	Does not reply	Does not know
98. I have confidence in the professional ability of my GP							
99. I believe that my GP cares about me							
100. I feel comfortable consulting my GP about my doubts or health problems							
101. My GP understands what I tell him/her about my health							
102. The information my GP gives me is easy to understand							
103A. The information my GP gives me is sufficient							
103B. Why?						___	___
104. When I request an appointment with the GP, I always see the same doctor							
105A. I would recommend my GP to my family and friends							
105B. Why?						___	___

Specialists	Totally agree	Agree	Disagree	Totally disagree	Not applicable	Does not reply	Does not know
106. I have confidence in the professional ability of the specialists treating me							
107. I believe that the specialists care about me							
108. I feel comfortable consulting the specialists about my doubts							
109. The specialists understand what I tell them about my health							
110. The information the specialists give me is easy to understand							
111A. The information the specialists give me is sufficient							
111B. Why?						___	___
112. When I request an appointment for the same health problem I am always seen by the same specialist							
113A. I would recommend my specialists to my family and friends							
113B. Why?						___	___

E. GENERAL MORBIDITY AND SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC DATA*FOR ALL PATIENTS INTERVIEWED***114. How would you describe your general health?**

1 Very good 2 Good 3 Fair 4 Poor 5 Very poor

115. What illnesses do you have? OPEN ENDED____

____**116. Where do you go when you are ill or need advice about your health?**1 Primary care centre 2 Hospital A&E 3 Private healthcare
4 Specialist 5 A&E at health centre/Clinic 6 Specialist in complementary medicine
7 Friends or family 8 Other. Specify:**117. Sex** 1 Female 2 Male**118. Date of birth**

____/____/____

119. Where were you born?

1 Spain → go to question 122 2 Other. Specify country:

120. What is your nationality? OPEN ENDED____
____**121. How long have you lived in Spain?**

Months: _____ or Years: _____

122. What is your profession? OPEN ENDED____
____**123. What is your current job? OPEN ENDED**____
____**124. What is your academic level? OPEN ENDED**____
____**125A. Do you have any private health insurance?**

1 Yes 2 No → Go to comments 98 Does not reply → Go to comments 99 Does not know → Go to comments

125B. What insurance do you have?**Would you like to make any further comments? PATIENT'S COMMENTS**.....
.....
.....
.....